

ISSN 2455-393X

Journal of the English Literator Society

Volume 12 Issue 1, January 2026 | www.jels.in

Research Article

From Kitchen to Community: How *Axone* Exposes Racism Against Northeast Indians in Urban India

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Published online: 5 January 2026

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18145712>

ABSTRACT

This paper examines the Netflix film *Axone* (2019) as a cultural text that exposes the everyday racism experienced by people from the Northeast living in mainland India's metropolitan cities. Through the symbolic use of *akhuni*, a fermented soybean dish central to the narrative, the film reveals how Northeast Indians' food habits and cultural differences provoke prejudice and stereotyping. Drawing on the theoretical frameworks of identity politics, cultural representation, and everyday racism, this study explores how *Axone* depicts the struggles of Northeastern migrants in mainland India as cultural "aliens" from the far Northeast region. Using qualitative film analysis and thematic interpretation, the paper argues that *Axone* documents microaggressions, discrimination, and the structural exclusion of an entire region within mainland India. The film also highlights community solidarity among people from Northeast India as a vital mechanism of survival. In this context, *Axone* functions as a critical cinematic intervention that challenges dominant metropolitan narratives and urges a reconsideration of race, identity, and cultural coexistence in contemporary India.

KEYWORDS: Racism, Cultural Representation, Food and Othering, Microaggressions

FULL PAPER

Introduction

Northeast India is situated in the easternmost part of the country. The region is recognised as one of the most culturally and ethnically diverse parts of the country. Bollywood movies frequently resort to tokenism in depicting Northeast India as an exotic “other” territory inhabited by underdeveloped, illiterate, violent, and primitive tribal groups. Furthermore, Bollywood films resort to stereotyping, cultural appropriation, and exotification of the nation’s periphery region under the guise of a realistic portrayal of life in the region.

Bollywood movies represent people from Northeast India as tribal and indigenous stereotypes in the narrative. The Bollywood film industry in Mumbai frequently employs stereotypes, caricatures, and typecasting to depict ethnic cultures, indigenous populations, tribal individuals, and communities. The tribal and indigenous people in the narrative of Bollywood movies are subjected to both positive and negative racial stereotypes. The positive stereotypes of Bollywood films include the portrayal of the indigenous characters as innocent, infantile, strong, and inherently beautiful. Conversely, the negative stereotype includes the depiction of them as murderous terrorists, irrational warriors, savage, uncultured, immoral, wild, uncivilised, and illiterate brutes residing in hilly regions. In addition, Bollywood movies create stereotypes around the distinct customs, habits, lifestyles, and manners of tribal and indigenous people from Northeast India. This stereotyping and othering of tribal and indigenous characters in the narrative are manifested in the mongoloid physical attributes, costume choices, athletic physique, exotic culinary practices, English fluency, accented Hindi, consumption of addictive substances, and taste for music and sports. In addition, the incidence of microaggressions and racial oppression endured by individuals from Northeast India is incorporated as obligatory scenes in the narrative of Bollywood movies. Therefore, racial profiling of tribal and indigenous people from the Northeast in the metropolises of mainland India is a recurrent pattern in Bollywood movies.

Bollywood movies frequently resort to othering and stereotyping characters from Northeast India in their narratives. The othering and stereotyping of indigenous characters from Northeast India is manifested in the narrative through a recurring pattern of characterization. In the narrative, Bollywood movies frequently portray characters from Northeast India as stereotypes of foreigners from neighbouring Southeast Asian nations. Most often, there is no proper identification or mention of the characters' community affiliations. The characters are simply designated as people from the “Northeast” or accorded identical physical attributes. Therefore, racial labelling, appropriation, and homogenization are observed as predominant practices

in Bollywood films depicting characters from the Northeast. This is evident in how the characters from Northeast India are assigned predominant personality traits.

The Netflix-released film *Axone: A Recipe for Disaster* is a 2019 comedy-drama film directed by Nicholas Kharkongor. The film features an ensemble cast from Northeast India. The film features Bollywood actors Lin Laishram, Tenzin Dalha, Sayani Gupta, Vinay Pathak, Dolly Ahluwalia, and others. The film depicts the “lived experiences” of a group of migrant youths from different parts of Northeast India living as tenants in Humayunpur, South Delhi. The film depicts how a group of youths from Northeast India encounter everyday racism and microaggressions from mainland Indian tenants because of their distinct culinary practices, lifestyle, and fashion.

Objective of the Study:

The study is based on the hypothesis that Bollywood movies reinforce stereotypes about people from Northeast India in their narratives. In the narrative, characters from Northeast India are portrayed as “outsiders” in the mainland Indian settings. This paper uses the Netflix-released movie *Axone* as a case study to analyse how racism, stereotyping, and identity politics intersect within urban India. It seeks to answer the question: How does *Axone* portray everyday racism experienced by Northeast Indians in urban Indian spaces through the lens of food, culture, and social interaction?

The paper examines the issues of everyday racism, microaggressions, othering, and the objectification of characters from Northeast India in the narrative of the *Axone*. The study is qualitative and descriptive, presenting a close textual and visual analysis of the film, along with an analysis of its themes. Philomena Essed’s concept of everyday racism serves as a theoretical framework for understanding the experiences of people from Northeast India in mainland India’s metropolitan cities, as represented in the film.

Discussing Racism in Social Discourse

Stereotypes are frequently created around racial categories. Thus, the act of stereotyping is closely related to the discourse of “race.” There has been extensive discussion on whether race is innately biological or a cultural construct. However, contemporary scholarship on race theory asserts that the concept of race is inherently political and power-laden. According to Guy P. Harrison, categorising humans into racial-genetic ancestral groups is not scientific, as race is just a cultural creation rather than a biological reality. “Biological races are not real; socially constructed races are very real” (Harrison 34). Stuart Hall argues that the racial categorization of whites and blacks is nothing but a set of binary oppositions created by those in power. “A set of binary oppositions structures this racialized discourse. There is the powerful opposition between ‘civilisation’ (white) and ‘savagery’ (black)” (Hall 243). John

McLeod also contends that the creation of racial difference is endowed with political significance:

...it is important to realise that all constructions of racial differences are based upon human invention and not biological fact. There exists no objective criterion by which human beings can be neatly grouped into separate 'races', each fundamentally different from the other. Racial differences are best understood as political constructions that serve the interests of certain groups. (McLeod 110)

The American Association of Physical Anthropology asserts that the concept of race has contributed to racist ideologies. The Association argues that the concept of race has resulted in the propagation of notions of cultural stereotypes, racial profiling, and ethnocentric assumptions of superiority and inferiority. The association contends that the categorization of human beings into different racial groups only works as a mechanism to rationalize exploitation, oppression, discrimination, and structural racism.

Racial categories do not accurately reflect human biological variation. Variation exists within and among populations across the planet, and patterns of similarity and difference can differentiate groups of individuals. However, these patterns do not align with socially defined racial groups (such as whites and blacks) or continentally defined geographic clusters (such as Africans, Asians, and Europeans). What has been characterized as "race" does not constitute discrete biological groups or evolutionarily independent lineages. (Fuentes et al. 401)

In the article "Racism and Nationalism," Etienne Balibar expresses two forms of racism: external and internal racism. He defines external racism as a manifestation of xenophobia directed towards people who are located outside the borders of the nation on the grounds of their 'race.' He refers to internal racism as discrimination and prejudice directed at individuals and groups living within the nation through exclusion as not belonging to the imagined community of the nation-state.

The act of stereotyping and racial division perpetuates the "othering" of individuals, groups, communities, and societies. "In general terms, the 'other' is anyone separate from one's self" (Ashcroft et al. 154). Edward Said examined the phenomenon of "othering" that Western knowledge discourses perpetuated regarding the colonised subject. Said asserts that the process of othering the Orient reinforces binary dichotomies of the concepts of self and other, representing the West and East, respectively. Gayatri Chakravarty Spivak coined the term "othering" to refer to the discursive practice of Western colonisers to colonise, exclude, and marginalise the natives as geographical and racial others. Alison Mountz views "othering" as the practice that marginalises, separates, discriminates, excludes, or labels an individual or

a group as outside the centre. “‘Othering’ is the process that makes the other. The process of creating the ‘other’ wherein persons or groups are labelled as deviant or non-normative happens through the constant repetition of characteristics about a group of people who are distinguished from the norm in some way” (Gallaher et al. 328).

Stereotyping and othering individuals into racial categories are linked with structural relations of power and authority. The powerful groups resort to the practices of creating stereotypes and othering individuals and groups to denigrate, exclude, and marginalise them as inferior “others” in the social discourse. In this, certain groups of people are bracketed and grouped into categories based on signifiers such as skin colour, physical attributes, and cultural signifiers such as costume choices, food habits, and hairstyle.

Philomena Essed, in her groundbreaking work *Understanding Everyday Racism: An Interdisciplinary Theory* (1991), writes about racism as an everyday and lived experience for people of Black African descent. She argues that the concept of everyday racism refers to the routine, normalized, and often subtle ways in which racism is experienced and reproduced in daily life—at workplaces, in neighbourhoods, schools, housing, and public spaces. Furthermore, Essed highlights that everyday racism is manifested through subtle forms of stereotyping, racialised jokes and comments, suspicion, surveillance, and the exclusion of Black Africans within predominantly White societies.

...everyday life in a white-dominated society involves a continual battle against the denial of racism, against Whitecentrism, against automatic in-group preference among whites, against constant impediments to their aspirations, against humiliations, against petty harassment, and against denigration of their cultures. (Essed 10)

The concept of everyday racism can be applied to a discussion of the film *Axone*, as characters from Northeast India are shown to experience racism and stereotyping from people from mainland India. In the narrative, everyday racism is manifested in the form of racial slurs, microaggressions related to physical appearance, mockery of the characters’ names, and constant surveillance of migrant youths from the region. Most importantly, the film shows how the distinct food habits of Northeastern migrant youths result in their encountering racist slurs, prejudice, and stereotyping. This policing of food habits becomes a significant marker of everyday racism.

The film *Axone* follows a single day in the lives of a group of migrant youths from Northeast India who are staying as tenants in a South Delhi neighbourhood. On a special occasion, the group prepares to cook *akhuni* with pork. They intend to celebrate Minam's (Asenla Jamir) wedding by preparing *akhuni*. The *axone*, or *akhuni*,

is a pungent-smelling fermented soybean dish of Nagaland's Sema (Sumi) tribe. The pungent smell of the ethnic dish enrages the landlord and the neighbours. The landlord and neighbours scold and threaten them. The rest of the narrative revolves around their arduous quest for a suitable location to prepare the cuisine. Thus, the film explores the politics around the culinary practices of indigenous people living in mainland India. In addition, the film portrays how people from Northeast India experience ethnic slurs, unwanted gazes, stereotypes, and prejudices in mainland India.

The film establishes the urban cityscape of Delhi with a bird's-eye view shot of tall skyscrapers, apartment complexes, and city streets. In numerous scenes, a tribal humming tune is used as background music to establish the characters from Northeast India in the metropolis. Extra characters with mongoloid physical traits appear in several scenes. Props are deployed to establish the characters' ethnic identities from Northeast India. In the opening scene, a few advertising posters and signboards bearing the word "Northeast" are captured in extreme close-up. In numerous scenes, the word "India" is prominently displayed through props such as posters and wall writing. In some scenes, mainland Indian characters are captured with newspapers that prominently display words such as "Bharat" and "Hindustan."

The film is one of the genuine attempts at depicting an authentic insight into the daily racism, hatred, violence, and discrimination experienced by people from Northeast India. The film dramatises multiple instances in which a group of young individuals from Northeast India encounter racism, sexual molestation, and bigotry. The film depicts how the mongoloid attributes of people from Northeast India attract casual racism and discrimination as foreigners and outsiders. The film also depicts how people from Northeast India encounter objectified gaze, racist slurs, and microaggressions from mainland Indians as individuals from neighbouring Southeast Asian nations. The film shows that some of the racist slurs encountered by tribal people from Northeast India include 'Chinky,' 'Momo,' and 'Chow-mein.' All these racist slurs and microaggressions tend to imply their phenotypical similarity with Chinese people.

The film examines the politics of indigenous people's culinary habits in metropolitan cities. The film explores the issue of racial oppression and eviction threats encountered by a group of migrant youths from Northeast India because of their unique cuisine.

The film *Axone* by Nicholas Kharkongor uses the food motif to explore complex issues such as cultural acceptance, preservation, and resistance in a multicultural world. In this film, food becomes the main point of difference that caused racist treatment towards the group of Northeast migrants who wanted to prepare their ethnic food for one of their friends' weddings. (Bora 3)

The film's subtitle, "A Recipe for Disaster," foreshadows the events to unfold in the narrative. The film shows that preparing unique ethnic dishes in metropolises is an arduous task for tribal people. In the rented apartments of Chanbi (Lin Laishram) and Upasana (Sayani Gupta), the migrant youths encounter racial slurs and eviction threats from the landlady Mata Ji (Dolly Ahluwalia) and neighbours for preparing *axone*. The eviction threat leads her to experience a panic attack. The following dialogue sequence demonstrates how people from Northeast India are outcasts in the metropolitan areas:

NEIGHBOUR MAN 1: Who are you? Speak up. Why are you lying? You think that we do not know the source of the smell coming from your room. You are lying and not even apologizing to Aunty (Land Lady). Say sorry to her.

CHANBI: Sorry Aunty. This will not happen again.

NEIGHBOUR MAN 1: If you do it again, we will throw you out. The same thing happened in Munirka.

NEIGHBOUR MAN 2: What happened in Munirka?

NEIGHBOUR MAN 1: Everyone decided that these people will not be provided houses on rent. Problem solved. (*Axone* 00.35.35-00.36.35)

In this pivotal scene, high-angle shots are used to frame Chanbi, emphasising her vulnerability in the mainland Indian setting. Besides, extreme close-up shots capture her traumatic and anguished expression. In addition, handheld shots in the scene intensify the tension. This eviction threat leads Chanbi to seek medical advice for her panic attack.

The film also poses the pertinent question of the right to prepare ethnic dishes in the metropolitan areas of the country. It raises the question of whether people from Northeast India have the right to cook food of their choice. In an important scene, Chanbi and Upasana pay a visit to the house of one of their friends, Martha (Pui). This woman, Martha, is from Northeast India and is married to a Punjabi man. They seek Martha's advice to find a place to cook *axone*. She raises the issue of rights.

MARTHA: These things create a lot of tension between us and them.

CHANBI: We have the right to cook our food.

MARTHA: They have the right not to suffer the smell of our food. Now, whose right is right? Tell me. (*Axone* 00:50:20-40)

In this way, the film sheds light on how indigenous people from Northeast India encounter racial oppression due to their unique ethnic food habits. The film also depicts the secrecy surrounding the sale of *axone* and pork in mainland India. In a scene, Chanbi and Upasana, with their friend Zorem (Tenzin Dalha), visit a house to

buy *axone* and pork. The house they visit is a dingy, one-story smokehouse in an unidentified locality. The man in the house, with mongoloid features, cast a mysterious gaze at them. He shows his suspicion to the two girls accompanying Zorem. The low-key lighting, smoky air, and the narrow alleys leading to the house enhance the mystery of the place. The flickering red light in the room evokes a sense of urgency and unease. All these highlight the peril associated with selling *axone* and pork in mainland India.

The film features numerous instances where individuals from Northeast India are subjected to racist slurs and microaggressions. In an important scene, the landlady's son, Shiv (Rohan Joshi), casually comments that they are friends. He says, "*Hindi-Chini Bhai Bhai*" (Indian and Chinese are brothers). This comment from Shiv tends to cast individuals from Northeast India as people of Chinese descent. In another scene, Zorem is called "Danny" by the landlord (Vinay Pathak). Racist epithets and prejudiced comments are also made about the small eyes of people from the Northeast. In a scene, the landlady resorts to casual racism in her remark about Bendang's small eyes. She says, "Look, he cannot even open his eyes."

The film depicts that racist slurs and microaggressions are not limited to Northeast Indians. All people with distinct mongoloid physical attributes encounter racist microaggressions despite their caste affiliation. Bunty Singh (Jimpa Bhutia), the indigenous woman Martha's son, has a mongoloid facial structure inherited from his mother. The mongoloid physiognomy of the Punjabi boy Bunty is also a target of racist slurs. He also encounters racist slurs for his small eyes. In one scene, a lady from mainland India asks him, "Can you see the whole wall with those small eyes?" The experience of casual racism by individuals from Northeast India is also dramatised in the scene when an elderly man claims that all the people from the region look the same. In an important scene in the film, the elderly man Vivek Mansukhani, in his cameo appearance, hurls a racist slur at the group of migrant youths. He casually says, "All of you look the same." (*Axone* 00:43:15-45)

The indigenous communities from Northeast India are also subjected to racist jibes due to their ethnic costume choices. In the final sequence, the group of migrant youths is seen adorned in traditional ethnic costumes for the marriage party. It is here that they encounter racist slurs from the residents of the Humayunpur locality.

Lady 1: Are you going to a fancy dress party?

Man 1: Look, look! Fashion parade at Granny's house!

Man 2: Is it Jackie Chan's birthday?

Lady 2: Where are you going all decked up?

Man 2: Are we invited? (*Axone* 01:20:10-01:20:30)

In the film, numerous scenes feature a hookah-smoking old man seated in a corner of the neighbourhood street. The man keeps staring at the youths from Northeast India. Acclaimed Bollywood actor Adil Hussain plays the role of this old man in his cameo. He does not have a dialogue in the narrative. This old man is often seen reading a newspaper with the word “Hindustan” prominently displayed. He silently continues to gaze at the migrant youths. The character's silent gaze on the migrant youths from Northeast India serves as a witness to their every movement. It also reveals how individuals from Northeast India endure perpetual surveillance by mainland Indians. In a review of the film, Devansh Sharma writes that Adil Hussain's character embodies the inquisitive gaze of mainstream Indians on the Northeast community:

Adil Hussain chimes in a cameo as a Jat patriarch perennially seated outside Zorem's shop. He has no dialogue, but nails the expression of a curiously suspicious watchdog. One does not mind his minor presence in the film because he aptly represents the prying eyes of the native population, fixated on every migrant activity. (Sharma)

The film depicts Bendang (Lanuakum Ao), a young man from Nagaland, who is mob lynched for his distinctive hairstyle. He is brutally thrashed by the residents of Lajpat Nagar in New Delhi for his exotic hairstyle. The experience of racist violence has left him with enduring emotional trauma. He frequently suffers from paranoia, low self-esteem, and recurring anxiety attacks. Bendang's emotional anguish goes to the extent that he is unable to protest against the sexist jibes and molestation of his girlfriend.

Continuous discrimination has shaken Bendang's self-worth and self-confidence. The behavior of Bendang can be related to social anxiety disorder, that is, the fear of negative evaluation, the fear of embarrassment, which partially comes from his earlier non-acceptance. The effect of the incident is very much reflected in the behavior of Bendang when he remained numb even when his partner faced the same brutality. (Bora 5)

Bandang is frequently captured behind iron-barred walls. This suggests his sense of captivity in mainland India. In most scenes, he is captured in a high-angle shot to suggest his vulnerability. The film also depicts that the traumatic experience of violent racism in the past has left an indelible mark on his personality. He talks very little with his friends. He reveals to Chanbi his desire to leave the city and return to his hometown. He frequently visits the Ao Naga Pastor's (Immanuel Imti) house for motivation and courage. Hence, the character of Bendang represents the archetype of a traumatised, alienated, and oppressed tribal man from the Northeast. However, Bendang's mob lynching is not dramatised in the narrative. Only Zorem shows

Upasana video footage of the incident on his mobile phone. The voiceover in the video footage describes the mob lynching of Bendang in the following way:

Yet another shameful incident from Delhi. Our exclusive footage shows how Bendang Lonkumer from Nagaland was brutally beaten up in the crowded Lajpat Nagar market until he became unconscious. Our sources say he was picked on by some men at a dairy shop in Lajpat Nagar market, simply because he coloured his hair blonde. When Bendang protested, you can see how they attacked him with hockey sticks and rods. Look how they are beating him mercilessly! (*Axone* 01:08:37-01:09:50)

In an important scene, Bendang locks himself in a dark, dingy room. In the scene, low-key lighting emphasises Bendang's deep emotional anguish. The red light in the room enhances the apprehension of the tribal man, Bendang, in mainland India. The ominous background score in the scene also intensifies Bendang's profound emotional trauma.

In a review of the film, Kaustubh Deka objects that the film has weakened the fight against racism by emphasising the message of submission and integration of people from the Northeast. He argues that the depiction of racial discrimination experienced by people from the Northeast in the narrative is an account presented from the perspective of the privileged. He presents his observation as follows:

It is 'racism' as felt and understood by a special section of the north-eastern migrants, a small but culturally influential elite. To decipher the cultural politics of *Axone*, one will have to realize that the often-assumed homogenous category of northeastern migrants is a multi-class lot in reality, and the lived experiences of this lot, their ways of interacting with the city, their aspirations, as well as struggles, sharply vary as per their class realities. Within this lot, the privileged—the elites of the region, a minuscule section wielding disproportionately large cultural influence—have been invested in a particular ideology of 'integration'. (Deka)

Kaustubh Deka argues that the film reveals "a classic case of victim blaming." He contends that this classic case of blaming the victim diminishes the persistent structural racism that people from Northeast India encounter in the metropolitan cities of the country. The film provides the solutions 'assimilation' and 'integration' to evade racism. In an important scene, Chanbi accuses Bendang of not integrating with mainland Indians, claiming that he has created his 'own Northeast' in Delhi.

CHANBI: All these years, you have not met one single friend from here. How sad is that, dude! You say you want to go back to the Northeast, but no, you make your own Northeast right here. You only interact with people from the Northeast. Some of them might have a problem with us, but no, most of them are nice to us, you know, and that is the reason you and I were living here. (*Axone* 01:29:58-01:31:01)

In his first appearance, Bendang is seen rehearsing a Hindi song, “Uthe sab ki kadam” (everyone steps up), in a dark, dingy room. He is upset because he cannot hum the tune correctly. He expresses his frustration by discarding the sheet of paper on which the song is written. According to Munmi Bora, Bendang’s attempt to sing a Hindi song is an example of an attempt to integrate with the dominant culture. Bendang is attempting to integrate into mainland Indian culture by learning to sing a Hindi song.

The film perpetuates othering and stereotyping around characters from Northeast India through mongoloid physical attributes and tribal physiognomy. Here, the film tends to homogenise and exoticise all people from Northeast India as a tribal population. In addition, the depiction of numerous episodes of racist slurs and microaggressions encountered by characters from the Northeast reinforces the tribal stereotype of the exotic “other.”

The film misrepresents the marriage ritual of the Galo community of Arunachal Pradesh. The film depicts the Galo community's practice of ‘bride replacement.’ The Galo community objected, saying that this practice is not part of their culture. In a review of the film, Gertrude Lamare writes that the representatives of the Galo Welfare Society (GWS) issued a legal notice to the director of *Axone* for their alleged “unethical and slanderous depiction of a fundamental marriage ritual practice.” (Lamare).

Conclusion:

In the film *Axone*, the marginalisation of a group of migrant youths from Northeast India is brought to the forefront through a day-in-the-life narrative of Northeastern migrants preparing *akhuni*, a traditional fermented soybean dish, for a friend’s wedding. The film serves as a crucial cinematic intervention that exposes the racialised experiences of Northeast Indians in urban India. Through its narrative centred on food, the film highlights how people from Northeast India encounter everyday racism in mainland Indian cities. The film underscores the need for broader societal recognition of Northeast Indian identities in metropolitan cities. In this way, *Axone* encourages a rethinking of race, identity, and belonging in contemporary India.

Works Cited

Ashcroft, Bill, et al., editors. *Post-Colonial Studies: The Key Concepts*. Second, Routledge, 2007, doi:10.4324/978023777855.

Axone. Directed by Nicholas Kharkongor, 2019.

Bora, Munmi. “Cultural Differences, Racism and Trauma : A Critical Analysis of Nicholas Kharkongor’s *Axone* : A Recipe for Disaster.” *Rupkatha Journal*, vol. 14, no. 2, 2022, pp. 1–10, doi:https://dx.doi.org/10.21659/rupkatha Journal.

Deka, Kaustubh. *Axone Is a Story of Racism Told From the Eyes of the Privileged*. 2020, <https://thewire.in/film/axone-movie-review-racism-privilege>.

Essed, Philomena. *Understanding Everyday Racism: An Interdisciplinary Theory*. Sage Publications, 1991.

Fuentes, Agustín, et al. "AAPA Statement on Race and Racism." *American Journal of Physical Anthropology*, vol. 169, no. 3, Wiley-Liss Inc., July 2019, pp. 400–02, doi:10.1002/AJPA.23882.

Gallaher, Carolyn, et al. "Key Concepts in Political Geography." *Procuring Penetration Testing Services*, First, Sage Publications Ltd., 2009, doi:10.2307/j.ctt155j45x.4.

Hall, Stuart. "The Spectacle of the 'Other.'" *Representation: Cultural Representations and Signifying Practices*, edited by Stuart Hall, First, Sage Publications, 1997, pp. 223–90.

Harrison, Guy P. *Race and Reality - What Everyone Should Know About Our Biological Diversity*. First, Prometheus Books, 2010, <http://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=cin20&AN=146131059&site=ehost-live>.

Lamare, Gertrude. "Can We Keep Talking Axone Please?" *Raiot.Com*, 2020, <https://raiot.in/can-we-keep-talking-axone-please/>.

McLeod, John. "Beginning Postcolonialism." *Viva Books*, Fifth, Manchester University Press, 2018.

Sharma, Devansh. "Axone Movie Review: A Clever yet Meandering Satire on Discrimination against Northeast Migrants in Delhi." *Firstpost.com*, 2020, <https://www.firstpost.com/entertainment/axone-movie-review-a-clever-yet-meandering-satire-on-discrimination-against-northeast-migrants-in-delhi-8463831.html>.